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2. Djuraeva Kamola Stanislavovna, Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna MODERN ASPECTS OF WHOOPING COUGH.....	10
3. F.E. Matyakubova, G.B. Mustaeva, O.S. Tirkashev, N.T.Rabbimova STUDY OF CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF ACUTE INTESTINAL INFECTIONS IN PREGNANT WOMEN.....	16
4. Ibadov Ravshan Aliyevich, Ibragimov Sardor Khamdamovich, Ergashev Sukhrob Panji o'gli THE IMPACT OF PREOPERATIVE COVID-19 INFECTION ON EARLY POSTOPERATIVE RESULTS IN MITRAL VALVE REPLACEMENT.....	23
5. O.S. Tirkashev, F.E. Matyakubova, N.T.Rabbimova, G.B. Mustaeva SPECIFIC CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE INTESTINAL INFECTIONS WITH HEMOCOLITIS SYNDROME IN EARLY CHILDHOOD.....	31
6. Эльнора А. Абдуганиева, Ирина В. Ливерко, Шахбосхон М. Ахмедов, Юлия Э. Фаттахова, Шоира Г. Матрзаева, Дильноза М. Халилова РОЛЬ ГИПЕРКОАГУЛЯЦИОННЫХ СОСТОЯНИЙ КАК ОСНОВНОЙ ПРИЧИНЫ ФАТАЛЬНЫХ ИСХОДОВ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ОБСТРУКТИВНОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ ЛЕГКИХ.....	35
7. N.T.Rabbimova, F.E. Matyakubova, O.S. Tirkashev, G.B. Mustaeva THE ROLE OF S. PNEUMONIAE IN EXCERNATION OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE.....	40
8. Djuraeva Kamola Stanislavovna, Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna MODERN ASPECTS OF WHOOPING COUGH.....	46
9. Eshonkhodjaev Otabek Djuraevich, Rakhimiy Sharif Uktamovich MODERN APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MEDISTINAL TUMORS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	52
10. Najmutdinova D.K., Nasirova A.K., Rasulov A.D. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AUTOIMMUNE THYROIDITIS AND VON WILLEBRAND FACTOR AND ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION...60	60

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AUTOIMMUNE THYROIDITIS AND VON WILLEBRAND FACTOR AND ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) is one of the most common endocrine disorders, often leading to hypothyroidism. The disease has a significant prevalence and most frequently affects women. Despite significant advances in understanding the pathogenesis of AIT, unresolved issues remain regarding the mechanisms of disease development and its impact on other body systems, including the cardiovascular system. An important aspect is the assessment of the hemostatic system in patients with AIT, particularly the level of von Willebrand factor (vWF), which plays a key role in platelet adhesion to damaged endothelial surfaces and the stabilization of factor VIII. Von Willebrand factor is a marker of endothelial dysfunction, which in turn is an early predictor of cardiovascular diseases. Changes in vWF levels may indicate the presence of inflammatory processes and disturbances in the hemostatic system, making it an important object of study in AIT.

Objective: To assess the levels of von Willebrand factor in patients with different phases of AIT and investigate its role in the development of endothelial dysfunction.

Material and methods: The study included 113 patients with AIT and 94 healthy individuals as a control group. The levels of von Willebrand factor were determined using immunological methods. Data analysis was performed to identify changes in von Willebrand factor levels depending on the phase of the disease.

Results: In patients with euthyroidism, the level of von Willebrand factor ($105.40 \pm 23.44\%$) was similar to the control group ($106.74 \pm 24.85\%$). Subclinical hypothyroidism showed a moderate decrease in von Willebrand factor levels to $93.75 \pm 26.80\%$, indicating initial changes in the hemostasis system. Manifest hypothyroidism was accompanied by a significant decrease in von Willebrand factor levels to $40.38 \pm 7.09\%$, indicating pronounced hemostatic disturbances. In hyperthyroidism, von Willebrand factor levels sharply increased to $172.11 \pm 15.94\%$, which was associated with an increased risk of thromboembolic complications.

Conclusion: The findings highlight the importance of monitoring von Willebrand factor levels in patients with AIT for timely diagnosis and correction of hemostatic disturbances. Regular observation and treatment adjustments can improve the prognosis and quality of life for patients.

Keywords: autoimmune thyroiditis, von Willebrand factor, endothelial dysfunction, hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, cardiovascular diseases.

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ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ АУТОИММУННОГО ТИРЕОИДИТА С ФАКТОРОМ ВИЛЛЕБРАНДА И ЕГО РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ ЭНДОТЕЛИАЛЬНОЙ ДИСФУНКЦИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение: Аутоиммунный тиреоидит (АИТ) является одним из наиболее распространённых эндокринных нарушений, часто приводящих к гипотиреозу. Заболевание имеет значительное распространение и чаще всего поражает женщин. Несмотря на значительные достижения в изучении патогенеза АИТ, остаются нерешёнными вопросы, связанные с пониманием механизмов развития заболевания и его влияния на другие системы организма, включая сердечно-сосудистую систему. Важным аспектом является оценка состояния системы гемостаза у пациентов с АИТ, в частности, уровня фактора Виллебранда (vWF), который играет ключевую роль в адгезии тромбоцитов к поврежденной эндотелиальной поверхности и стабилизации фактора VIII. Фактор Виллебранда является маркером эндотелиальной дисфункции, которая в свою очередь, является ранним предиктором сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний. Изменения в уровне vWF могут свидетельствовать о наличии воспалительных процессов и нарушениях в системе гемостаза, что делает его важным объектом исследования при АИТ.

Цель исследования: Оценить уровень фактора Виллебранда у пациентов с различными фазами АИТ и изучить его роль в развитии эндотелиальной дисфункции.

Материалы и методы исследования: В исследование включены 113 пациентов с АИТ и 94 здоровых лица, составивших контрольную группу. Уровень фактора Виллебранда определяли с помощью иммунологических методов. Анализ данных проводился с целью выявления изменений в уровне фактора Виллебранда в зависимости от фазы заболевания.

Результаты исследования: У пациентов с эутиреозом уровень фактора Виллебранда ($105,40 \pm 23,44\%$) был схож с контрольной группой ($106,74 \pm 24,85\%$). При субклиническом гипотиреозе наблюдалось умеренное снижение уровня фактора Виллебранда до $93,75 \pm 26,80\%$, что свидетельствует о начальных изменениях в системе гемостаза. Манифестный гипотиреоз сопровождался значительным снижением уровня фактора Виллебранда до $40,38 \pm 7,09\%$, указывая на выраженные нарушения гемостаза. При гипертиреозе уровень фактора Виллебранда резко повышался до $172,11 \pm 15,94\%$, что ассоциировалось с повышенным риском тромбоэмболических осложнений.

Заключение: Полученные данные подчеркивают важность мониторинга уровня фактора Виллебранда у пациентов с АИТ для своевременной диагностики и коррекции нарушений гемостаза. Регулярное наблюдение и корректировка лечения могут улучшить прогноз и качество жизни пациентов.

Ключевые слова: аутоиммунный тиреоидит, фактор Виллебранда, эндотелиальная дисфункция, гипотиреоз, гипертиреоз, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания.

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AUTOIMMUN TIREOIDIT VA VON WILLEBRAND OMILI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK VA UNING ENDOTELIAL DISFUNKTSIYANI RIVOJLANISHIDAGI ROLI

ANNOTATSIYA

Kirish: Autoimmun tireoidit (AIT) eng ko‘p uchraydigan endokrin buzilishlardan biri bo‘lib, ko‘pincha gipotireozga olib keladi. Kasallik keng tarqalgan bo‘lib, asosan ayollar kasallanadi. AIT patogenezini o‘rganishda katta yutuqlarga erishilganiga qaramay, kasallik rivojlanishining mexanizmlari va uning organizmning boshqa tizimlariga, jumladan, yurak-qon tomir tizimiga ta‘siri bilan bog‘liq muammolar oxirigacha hal qilinmagan holda qolmoqda. Muhim jihat AIT bilan kasallangan bemorlarda gemostaz tizimini, xususan, zarar ko‘rgan endoteliy yuzalariga trombositlar yopishishini va VIII faktorni barqarorlashtirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydigan von Willebrand omili (vWF) darajasini baholashdir. Von Willebrand omili endotelial disfunktsiyaning belgisi bo‘lib, o‘z navbatida, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining erta prediktori hisoblanadi. vWF darajasidagi o‘zgarishlar yallig‘lanish jarayonlari va gemostaz tizimidagi buzilishlarning mavjudligini ko‘rsatishi mumkin, bu esa uni AITda muhim tadqiqot ob‘ekti qiladi.

Tadqiqot maqsadlari: AITning turli fazalaridagi bemorlarda von Willebrand omili darajasini baholash va uning endotelial disfunktsiyani rivojlanishidagi rolini o‘rganish.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullar: Tadqiqotga AIT bilan og‘rigan 113 bemor va nazorat guruhi sifatida 94 sog‘lom shaxs kiritildi. Von Willebrand omili darajalari immunologik usullar yordamida aniqlangan. Ma‘lumotlar tahlili kasallik fazasiga qarab von Willebrand omili darajasidagi o‘zgarishlarni aniqlash uchun o‘tkazildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Eutireozdagi bemorlarda von Willebrand omili darajasi ($105,40 \pm 23,44\%$) nazorat guruhiga ($106,74 \pm 24,85\%$) o‘xshash edi. Subklinik gipotireozda von Willebrand omili darajasi $93,75 \pm 26,80\%$ gacha o‘rtacha kamaydi, bu gemostaz tizimida boshlang‘ich o‘zgarishlarni ko‘rsatadi. Manifest gipotireozda von Willebrand omili darajasining $40,38 \pm 7,09\%$ gacha sezilarli darajada pasayishi bilan kechdi, bu esa aniq ifodalangan gemostatik buzilishlarni ko‘rsatadi. Gipertireozda von Willebrand omili darajasi keskin oshib, $172,11 \pm 15,94\%$ ni tashkil etdi, bu tromboembolik asoratlar xavfining oshishi bilan bog‘liq edi.

Xulosa: Olingan ma‘lumotlar AIT bilan kasallangan bemorlarda gemostaz buzilishlarini o‘z vaqtida aniqlash va tuzatish uchun von Willebrand omili darajasini muntazam kuzatib borish muhimligini ta‘kidlaydi. Muntazam kuzatuv va davolashni moslashtirish bemorlarning prognozi va hayot sifatini yaxshilashi mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: autoimmun tireoidit, von Willebrand omili, endotelial disfunktsiya, gipotireoz, gipertireoz, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari.

Introduction

Autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) is considered one of the most common thyroid disorders. Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis (CAIT), in particular, frequently leads to the development of hypothyroidism. This disease affects 0.2-2% of the general population and 12-15% of individuals over the age of 50. Additionally, 10-15% of healthy individuals who do not suffer from thyroid dysfunction may have detectable antibodies to thyroid antigens. Among those affected, women predominate with a female-to-male ratio ranging from 4:1 to 10:1 [1,7,9].

Since 1998, thyroid diseases have consistently ranked first in the structure of overall endocrine morbidity among children and adolescents in the Republic of Uzbekistan. One of the earliest cases of AIT was described by H. Hashimoto in 1912. There are two main forms of the disease: hypertrophic and atrophic, each of which can lead to the development of hypothyroidism. Hypothyroidism is a clinical syndrome caused by a chronic deficiency of thyroid hormones. The prevalence of primary hypothyroidism is significant: the overt form occurs in 0.2%-2% of the population, while the subclinical form affects 7-10% of women and 2-3% of men [1,2,7].

Autoimmune thyroiditis is a key issue in modern endocrinology due to the complexities in understanding its developmental mechanisms, as well as the lack of precise and reliable diagnostic methods, including immunological approaches.

The pathogenesis of autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) can be attributed to both disruptions in immune control mechanisms and abnormalities in the structure of endocrine gland cells. These changes may be caused by genetic factors or may result from external conditions such as

environmental degradation, fluctuations in iodine levels in the body, radiation pollution, an increase in allergic reactions in the population, or the prevalence of viral infections [10,11].

Several mechanisms of autoimmune thyroid aggression triggered by excess iodine have been identified. These include: (1) the induction of autoreactive elements of the immune system causing a thyrotropic autoimmune effect; (2) the activation of free radical oxidation, leading to the presence of oxidized biomolecules in the thyroid gland; and (3) excessive iodination of thyroglobulin (TG). The genotype of the organism plays a decisive role in the realization of these mechanisms, which may operate either jointly or independently. In iodine-deficient countries, iodine deficiency disorders predominate in the structure of thyroid diseases, whereas in regions with adequate iodine supply, there is an increase in autoimmune thyroid pathology. This explains the significant variability in disease prevalence data and the differing opinions of authors regarding the impact of iodine prophylaxis on the growth of autoimmune thyroid pathology [8,12].

The analysis of current literature data shows that thyroid diseases are associated with an imbalance of several trace elements (selenium, zinc, copper, chromium, and others) involved in the synthesis of thyroid hormones and affecting iodine metabolism. It is known that the daily requirement for selenium ranges from 20 to 200 µg, depending on the region of residence. Selenium participates in the conversion of T4 to either reverse or active T3 as part of the enzyme deiodinase and also destroys excess hydrogen peroxide using glutathione peroxidase and thioredoxin reductase, thereby preserving the integrity of thyrocytes. Experimental selenium deficiency reduced the conversion of T4 to T3, proving the role of selenium in the action of thyroid hormones. The effect of selenium deficiency on thyroid hormone metabolism depends on whether it is due to selenium deficiency alone or a combination of iodine and selenium deficiencies. It has been proven that the use of selenium in the treatment of AIT influences, depending on the dosage, interleukin-2, tumor necrosis factor, gamma-interferon, and other cytokines involved in the development of AIT. Thus, selenium exerts direct and indirect anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects, as periodically observed in studies of human and animal immune cells. Adequate selenium intake affects the differentiation of T-cells into T-regulatory cells (T-reg) [3,12]. A reduction in the number or function of CD25+CD4+ T-reg cells leads to the development of AIT. The most important indicator is the determination of the titer of antithyroid antibodies, which in many cases of "idiopathic" hypothyroidism shows that AIT underlies it. The differential diagnosis of various forms of hypothyroidism is mainly based on laboratory indicators. AIT in the hypothyroid phase can present under various "masks."

Changes in the levels of thyroid hormones in the body lead to dysmetabolic alterations, contributing to the disruption of structural and functional relationships in various organs, primarily in the cardiovascular system. Clinical manifestations of cardiovascular disorders in hypothyroidism are characterized by complaints of polymorphic chest pain, dyspnea on exertion, and various nonspecific symptoms such as muscle weakness, reduced mental and physical activity, and edema of different locations. Hypothyroidism is often associated with cardiovascular diseases and is typically accompanied by lipid metabolism disorders, leading to dyslipidemia and an increased atherogenic index, as well as rhythm and conduction disturbances that are frequently resistant to antiarrhythmic therapy [5,6].

The initial stages of the atherosclerotic process are mediated by the development of endothelial dysfunction. Nitric oxide (NO) produced by endothelial cells induces the relaxation of vascular smooth muscle cells, which helps to reduce systemic vascular resistance; numerous endothelial factors regulate adhesion processes and blood coagulability. Low-grade chronic inflammation can reduce NO production, exacerbating oxidative stress in Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Endothelial dysfunction detection serves as an early and sensitive marker of cardiovascular disease risk.

In patients with metabolic syndrome associated with autoimmune thyroiditis, a reduction in endothelium-dependent and endothelium-independent vasodilation is observed. The most pronounced dyslipidemia is seen in patients with metabolic syndrome combined with autoimmune thyroiditis and subclinical hypothyroidism, compared to those with metabolic syndrome combined

with autoimmune thyroiditis and euthyroidism, and those with metabolic syndrome without thyroid disease.

An analysis of the literature and our own observations of patients with hypothyroidism, especially the subclinical variant, which often masks cardiovascular pathology, necessitates a focused study of this issue and the development of approaches to the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of hemodynamic changes in patients with hypothyroidism. According to the Rotterdam Study, subclinical hypothyroidism was associated with aortic atherosclerosis and myocardial infarction in older women, independent of cholesterol levels. Several other studies also confirm the link between subclinical hypothyroidism and the development of cardiovascular diseases, although some studies have not found a connection between subclinical hypothyroidism and increased cardiovascular risk.

Thyroid hormone deficiency causes metabolic changes that can disrupt the structural and functional relationships of various organs, especially affecting the cardiovascular system. Clinical manifestations of these disorders include complaints of diverse cardiac pain, dyspnea during physical activity, and other nonspecific symptoms such as muscle weakness, decreased activity, and edema. Hypothyroidism is often associated with cardiac disorders and lipid metabolism changes, leading to dyslipidemia and an increased atherogenic index.

An important factor is von Willebrand factor (vWF), a key element in the hemostatic system that ensures platelet adhesion to damaged endothelial surfaces and stabilizes factor VIII. An increase or decrease in vWF levels can indicate various pathological conditions, including endothelial dysfunction (ED), which plays a central role in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular diseases.

Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is characterized by an imbalance between vasodilating and vasoconstricting factors, leading to vasospasms, inflammation, and thrombosis. ED is associated with numerous cardiovascular diseases, such as arterial hypertension, coronary artery disease, chronic heart failure, peripheral artery disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and chronic kidney failure.

Von Willebrand factor (vWF) plays a crucial role in maintaining vascular integrity and endothelial function. The level of vWF increases in response to endothelial damage and inflammation, which is often observed during various phases of autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT). Thus, changes in vWF levels can serve as a marker of endothelial dysfunction and are associated with an increased risk of thrombosis and other cardiovascular complications in patients with AIT. An analysis of the literature and our own observations of patients with hypothyroidism, particularly the subclinical variant, which often masks cardiovascular pathology, necessitates a focused study of this issue and the development of approaches to the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of hemodynamic changes in patients with hypothyroidism [4,5].

Research Object

The study involved 113 patients with autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) in various phases of the disease, examined at the 3rd clinic of the consultative polyclinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy (TMA). The control group consisted of 94 healthy individuals.

Study Results

In our study, we analyzed the level of von Willebrand factor (vWF) in patients with different phases of autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) and in a control group of healthy individuals. The aim of this analysis was to identify changes in vWF levels depending on the phase of the disease and to assess their significance for the pathogenesis of endothelial dysfunction and related cardiovascular risks.

We established the important role of von Willebrand factor in hemostasis, ensuring platelet adhesion to damaged endothelial surfaces and stabilizing factor VIII. The level of von Willebrand factor can vary in different pathological conditions, including AIT, making it an important marker for study.

Table 1. Evaluation of von Willebrand Factor Levels in Various Phases of Autoimmune Thyroiditis

Indicator	Control Group (n=94)	Clinical Phase of Autoimmune Thyroiditis			
		Euthyroidism (n=65)	Subclinical Hypothyroidism (n=25)	Manifest Hypothyroidism (n=15)	Hyperthyroidism (n=8)
von Willebrand Factor (%)	106,74±24,85	105,40±23,44	93,75±26,80*	40,38±7,09*	172,11±15,94*

Note: * — statistically significant differences compared to control group indicators ($p < 0.05$).

According to our data, the von Willebrand factor level in patients with euthyroidism is $105.40 \pm 23.44\%$, which is almost identical to the control group's values of $106.74 \pm 24.85\%$. This indicates that with normal thyroid function, the von Willebrand factor level remains stable and within normal limits. Euthyroidism is characterized by the absence of clinically significant changes in hemostasis, as confirmed by the similarity in mean values and standard deviations with the control group. In the group of patients with subclinical hypothyroidism, a moderate decrease in von Willebrand factor levels to $93.75 \pm 26.80\%$ was observed. This decrease is statistically significant compared to the control group and the euthyroid group, indicating initial changes in the hemostatic system. Although clinical symptoms of hypothyroidism may not be pronounced, biochemical changes are already beginning to manifest. This may be related to inflammatory processes characteristic of autoimmune thyroiditis, which affect endothelial cells and the secretion of von Willebrand factor. In the group with overt hypothyroidism, the significant decrease in von Willebrand factor levels to $40.38 \pm 7.09\%$ indicates pronounced coagulation system disorders. This reduction is the most significant among all the studied groups and statistically differs from both the control group and other phases of AIT. Patients with overt hypothyroidism are at increased risk of bleeding, which is associated with insufficient von Willebrand factor secretion and other hemostatic changes. This fact underscores the need for active treatment and monitoring of thyroid hormone levels in these patients. In hyperthyroidism, a sharp increase in von Willebrand factor levels to $172.11 \pm 15.94\%$ was observed. This increase is statistically significant compared to the control group and all other phases of AIT. Hyperthyroidism is characterized by enhanced metabolic activity and inflammatory processes, which stimulate von Willebrand factor secretion by endothelial cells. Patients with hyperthyroidism are at risk of thromboembolic complications due to a hypercoagulable state, necessitating careful monitoring and possible adjustment of anticoagulant therapy.

Conclusion

The analysis of von Willebrand factor data in patients with autoimmune thyroiditis at different phases of the disease reveals significant changes in the hemostatic system. In euthyroidism, the von Willebrand factor level remains stable and corresponds to control values, while in subclinical hypothyroidism, moderate changes are observed, indicating initial disturbances. Overt hypothyroidism is accompanied by pronounced changes, requiring active treatment and control. Hyperthyroidism is characterized by a sharp increase in von Willebrand factor levels, indicating an increased risk of thromboembolic complications and the need for anticoagulant therapy. The obtained data underscore the importance of regular monitoring of hemostatic factor levels in patients with autoimmune thyroiditis for timely diagnosis and correction of abnormalities, which can improve the prognosis and quality of life of patients.

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